

Effects of music and sound waves on the evolutions of skin cells, collagen and elastin

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Abstract: Music waves could have the main role in evolutions of skin cells and controlling dermatologic diseases. These waves could enter into the auditory system, move hairs within Cochlear and produce electrochemical signals. These signals move along neurons, achieve to the hypothalamus and produce GnRH hormones. These hormones force into pituitary for producing LH and FSH. These new hormones go to Ovary in females and Testis in males and cause to creation of Estrogen, Progesterone and Testosterone. Estrogen is taken by special receptors on the skin cells and nucleus membranes, contributes in gene expression and produce collagen, elastin and melanin. Some music waves cause to the motion of charged particles around cells and production of electromagnetic and longitudinal waves. These waves pass the cell and nucleus gates and create more high energetic waves. Density of charged particles within the nucleus is more than density of charges around cells and more energetic currents are emerged. These currents produce waves with higher frequencies within the nucleus. These high frequency waves remove some repressors, active some genes and contribute in replication, transcription and translation. We test theory and show that intensity and frequencies of emitted waves of skin cells depend on the frequency of music waves. Also, these music waves need to a period of time to pass the cell and nucleus gates and contribute in gene expressions.

Keywords: Music, Skin, Wave, Hormone, Collegen

I. Introduction

Up to day, many scientists have asserted that there is a direct relation between music and human physiology and health. Some of main results are corresponded to effects of music waves on the skin cells and controlling dermatologic diseases. For example, in one study, authors have examined the impact of a cross-cultural musical program on young Portuguese adolescents' anti-dark-skin prejudice. Measures taken at the end of the programs have showed a reduction in anti-dark-skin prejudice, either implicit or explicit, among pupils in the experimental group and no reduction among pupils in the control group [1]. In

another research, the influence of rap music on African American girls' perceptions of skin color has been considered. Iterative coding and thematic analysis revealed rap music to be an influential purveyor of skin color messages, especially with regard to skin tone preferences [2]. In another investigation, university music and biology students' plasma levels of norepinephrine, endorphin, and Cortisol, and their galvanic skin responses were measured before and after listening to two different musical selections in an anechoic chamber and during controlled silence. The results indicated that biochemical variables changed significantly in both groups during listening to music but were not different during the controlled silence [3]. Some other authors have investigated the effects of 3 different genres of music in participants' Electrodermal Activity (EDA). They have shown that human emotion has a strong correlation with different types of music [4]. In another work, the authors have used music and meditation as stimuli in psychophysiological experiments using galvanic skin response (GSR) as an objective method to estimate the emotional response of subjects. Results have showed that GSR can be used as a measure of subjective mental states during music appreciation [5]. Now, the question arises that what is the relation between music waves and DNA waves within the skin cells?

Newly, it has been shown that DNAs could emit or receive waves and communicate with each other [6,7]. These biological objects have constructed from charged particles and consequently, by each motion of DNAs, some waves are emitted [8]. These waves are in direct relation with the structure of active genes and have the main role in gene expressions. To active genes for emitting waves, we can use of music waves. These music waves remove repressors, turn on genes, cause to radiation of waves and contribute in gene expression. This could be applied in curing diseases of skin.

The outline of paper is as follows: In section II, we propose some theoretical models for interaction of DNAs with skin cells. In section III, we introduce materials and suggest the experimental method. In section IV, we show the results and discuss about them. The last section is devoted to conclusion.

II. Theoretical Models

In this section, we show that music waves could have direct effects on the skin cells, contribute in transcription, translation and replication and control diseases.

To this aim, we consider mechanisms that music waves interact with DNAs of skin cells and force them to produce collagen, elastin and melanin. These mechanisms are:

1. Music waves arrive the ear, cause to motion of hairs within Cochlear and the emergence of electrochemical waves. These waves move along neurons and achieve to auditory cortex within the brain [9]. Then, they are exchanged between neural circuits of brain and achieve to Hypothalamus. Due to effects of these waves, Hypothalamus produce GnRH hormones which force into Pituitary for producing FSH and LH hormones [10,11]. These hormones go to Ovary in females and Testis in males and cause to creation of Estrogen, Progesterone and Testosterone [12,13]. Estrogen is taken by special receptors [14-16] on the skin cells and nucleus membranes and contributes in gene expression [17-19]. During these gene expressions, fibroblasts produce collagen and elastin [20,21] and melanocytes produce melanin [22](See figure 1).

Fig 1. Music waves cause to the production of some hormones which may have effects on the skin cells

2. In normal conditions, DNAs of keratinocytes and melanocytes exchange waves and communicate with each other. Each of these DNAs has been constructed from charged particles and by motion of these charges, some currents are emerged:

$$i = q V \quad (1)$$

Where i is the current, q is the charge and V is the velocity of charges. These currents move along an structure like the inductor and produce some electromagnetic waves:

$$B_{0-k} = \mu (n_k) i_k \quad (2)$$

Where B_{0-k} is the magnetic field which is produced along the DNA inductor of keratinocytes and n_k is the number of active genes. These waves could be received by other DNAs, cause to the motion of other charged particles and creation of extra currents. These currents act like the extra currents within the inductor and produce some new electromagnetic:

$$B_{0-m} = \mu (n_m) i_m \quad (3)$$

Where B_{0-m} is the magnetic field which is produced along the DNA inductor of melanocytes and n_m is the number of active genes within the melanocytes. In these inductors, non-active genes act like silent circles that don't contribute in sending or receiving waves (See Figure 2).

Fig 2. DNAs of keratinocytes and melanocytes exchange some waves with each other.

3. Music waves could enter into the nucleus of keratinocytes, remove repressors and active genes. These new active genes have constructed from charged particles and by their motions, some new currents are emerged. These currents move along the DNA inductors and produce some new electromagnetic fields. We can write:

$$B_{1-k} = \mu (n_k + m_k) i_k \quad (4)$$

Where B_{1-k} is the magnetic field which is produced along the DNA inductor of keratinocytes and m_k is the number of new active genes. These new fields are taken by other DNA inductors, cause to the motion of charged particles and emergence of new currents. These currents produce some new electromagnetic waves which contribute in gene expression. We can use of below equation:

$$B_{1-m} = \mu (n_m + m_m) i_m \quad (5)$$

Where B_{1-m} is the magnetic field which is produced along the DNA inductor of melanocytes and m_m is the number of new active genes within the melanocytes. These waves get away repressors, active genes and construct some main matters like melanin in melanocytes (See Figure 3).

Fig 3. Music waves could turn on some genes on the skin cells.

4. Music waves could contribute in gene expression through four stages (See Figure 4). A. First, music waves cause to the motion of charged particles. By motion of these charges, two types of waves are emerged. These waves are: 1. Electromagnetic waves 2. Longitudinal waves. Electromagnetic

waves are emerged by currents which are produced due to motion of charged particles. Longitudinal waves are emerged by longitudinal motions of charged particles. B. In second stage, these waves pass the gates and enter within the cells. These waves cause to the motion of charged particles within the cells and production of new electromagnetic and longitudinal waves. These new waves have more frequencies, because density of liquid molecules within the cell is more respect to the density of liquid molecules out of cells. This causes that energy of charged particles increase and frequency of waves grows. C: In third stage, these new high energy waves pass the nuclear gates and cause to the motions of charged particles within the nucleus. These motions cause to the production of more high energies currents and waves. Because density of particles within the nucleus is more respect to cells. We can write :

$$\begin{aligned}
q_{\text{out-cell}} &< q_{\text{within-cell}} < q_{\text{within-nucleus}} \\
V_{\text{out-cell}} &< V_{\text{within-cell}} < V_{\text{within-nucleus}} \\
I_{\text{out-cell}} = N_{\text{out-cell}} q_{\text{out-cell}} V_{\text{out-cell}} &< I_{\text{within-cell}} = N_{\text{within-cell}} q_{\text{within-cell}} V_{\text{within-cell}} \\
&< I_{\text{within-nucleus}} = N_{\text{within-nucleus}} q_{\text{within-nucleus}} V_{\text{within-nucleus}} \\
B_{\text{out-cell}} = \mu (n_{\text{out-cell}}) i_{\text{out-cell}} &< B_{\text{within-cell}} = \mu (n_{\text{within-cell}}) i_{\text{within-cell}} \\
&< B_{\text{within-nucleus}} = \mu (n_{\text{within-nucleus}}) i_{\text{within-nucleus}} \\
E_{\text{out-cell}} = h f_{\text{out-cell}} \sim (B_{\text{out-cell}})^2/2\mu &< E_{\text{within-cell}} = h f_{\text{within-cell}} \sim (B_{\text{within-cell}})^2/2\mu \\
&< E_{\text{within-nucleus}} = h f_{\text{within-nucleus}} \sim (B_{\text{within-nucleus}})^2/2\mu \quad (6)
\end{aligned}$$

Where $q_{\text{out-cell}}$, $q_{\text{within-cell}}$, $q_{\text{within-nucleus}}$ are charges out , within cells and within nucleus respectively, $V_{\text{out-cell}}$, $V_{\text{within-cell}}$, $V_{\text{within-nucleus}}$ are velocities out , within cells and within nucleus respectively, $N_{\text{out-cell}}$, $N_{\text{within-cell}}$, $N_{\text{within-nucleus}}$ are number of charges out , within cells and within nucleus respectively, $I_{\text{out-cell}}$, $I_{\text{within-cell}}$, $I_{\text{within-nucleus}}$ are currents out , within cells and within nucleus respectively, $B_{\text{out-cell}}$, $B_{\text{within-cell}}$, $B_{\text{within-nucleus}}$ are magnetic fields out , within cells and within nucleus respectively, $n_{\text{out-cell}}$, $n_{\text{within-cell}}$, $n_{\text{within-nucleus}}$ are number of currents out , within cells and within nucleus respectively, $E_{\text{out-cell}}$, $E_{\text{within-cell}}$, $E_{\text{within-nucleus}}$ are energies out , within cells and within nucleus respectively and finally $f_{\text{out-cell}}$, $f_{\text{within-cell}}$, $f_{\text{within-nucleus}}$ are frequencies out , within cells and within nucleus respectively.

Above equation shows that music waves produce very high energetic waves within the nucleus. These waves could make a pressure on

polymerase, force them towards to DNAs and cause to replication or transcription. Also, they can remove repressors and contribute in gene expressions (See Figure 4).

Fig 4. Music waves contribute in replication, transcription and translation.

III: Material and Method

To observe effects of music waves on the skin cells, we propose an experimental method. In this method, we need to:

1. Magnetic Detector
2. Wire
3. Magnet
4. Scope
5. Amperemeter
6. Piano or a device for producing music wave like a player
7. Graphene sheet
8. Skin cells

To take skin waves,

1. We provide a magnetic detector. This detector can be produced by a metal which two magnets are locating in opposite directions respect to it. These magnets produce two magnetic fields in opposite directions. These magnetic waves force to spinors within the metal and make them in parallel with external fields. Two opposite fields produce two anti-parallel spinors and create pairs. Any extra field can break these pairs and produce currents (See figure 1).
2. We can use of graphene sheet as a magnetic detector. To this aim, we produce some defects including pentagonal structures within the sheet. Number of charges within the pentagonal molecules is more respect to number of charges within hexagons and some currents are emerged between hexagons and pentagons. Any external field can produce extra currents which are taken by scopes (See figure 1).
3. We put a magnetic detector on the skin cells and connect it to an amperemeter and scope .
4. We turn on a music player or use of a device for producing music waves with different frequencies.
5. We measure currents which are emerged by skin waves by a magnetic detector.

Fig 5. Some detectors for skin waves

Fig 6. A circuit for considering effects of music waves on the skin waves.

IV: Results

We examine the model for two music waves with (440 and 432 Hz). We use of an scope for measuring the currents (J_{music}) which are emerged by music waves. Then, we connect a magnetic diode to the skin and measure the currents ($J_{skin+music}$) which are produced by skin waves and music. We obtain the currents which are emerged by skin cells.

$$J_{\text{skin}} = J_{\text{skin+ music}} - J_{\text{music}} \quad (7)$$

Where J_{skin} is the current which is emerged by skin cells, $J_{\text{skin+ music}}$ is the current which is emerged by both skin and music waves and J_{music} is the current which is emerged by music waves. In figure 7, we present radiated waves of skin which are taken by Radio-SkyPipe. It is clear that by passing time, intensity and picks of these waves grow. We also compare currents which are emerged by skin waves for two music waves (440 Hz (blue color) and 432 Hz (red color)) in figure 8. Obviously, by increasing frequency of music waves, the value of currents increases. Because, high energetic music waves cause to an increase in velocity of charged particles. On the other hand, each current has a direct relation with velocity of charged particles and fast particles produce higher values of currents. Also, by passing time, currents grow and tend to large values. This is because that eventually, music waves pass the cell gate and nucleus gate and make some genes active. These active genes produce new waves which cause to the production of new currents on the skin and magnetic detectors.

Fig 7. Radiated waves of skin could be taken by Radio-SkyPipe.

Fig 8. Currents which are emerged by skin waves in two frequencies of music waves.

V. Conclusion

In this research, we have proposed three methods that music waves could act on skin cells. In first method, music waves arrive the ear, move hairs within the cochlear and produce electrochemical waves. These waves move along neurons, go to hypothalamus and cause to the production of GnRH. This hormone enters into pituitary and leads to the production of FSH and LH. These hormones force to Ovary in females and Testis in males and cause to production of Estrogen, Progesterone and Testosterone. These hormones are attracted by receptors of skin cells, contribute in gene expression and cause to production of collagen, elastin and melanin. In second method, music waves pass the nuclear baskets and produce some extra currents within DNA inductors. Consequently, some extra DNA waves are emerged that remove repressors and make some genes active. These genes could produce collagen, elastin and melanin. In third method, music waves cause to the motion of charged particles around cells and the emergence of electromagnetic and longitudinal waves. These waves pass the cell and nucleus gates and cause to motion of particles and production of higher energetic currents. These currents produce some high energetic waves which contribute in transcription, translation and replication. We consider effect of music waves on the skin waves. We show that by increasing frequency of music

waves, frequency of skin waves increases. Also, currents which are emerged by music waves on the magnetic detector depend on time and by passing time, grow and tend to constant values.

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